

Does Quantum Wavelength Follow From Classical Entropy in the $T \rightarrow 0$ Limit?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Nov. 12, 2022

Ideas of entropy appeared before quantum mechanics was developed. In particular Planck introduced discrete energy levels: e_n where $e = \text{constant}$ and $n=1,2,3$ to describe allowed energies of an oscillator representing allowed light in a blackbody as shown in (1). In such a case average energy and entropy may be calculated using formulas from Boltzmann. In (1) it is shown that if continuous energy is used entropy is undefined as $T = \text{temperature} \rightarrow 0$ while entropy $\rightarrow 0$ as $T \rightarrow 0$ if there are discrete energy levels. As noted this problem applies to light and uses an oscillator model, but leads to the notion of discrete energy levels.

In this note we suggest using a particle in a box instead and consider only two levels for simplicity. We still use Boltzmann's probability factor $\exp(-\text{energy}(i)/T)$ where $i=1,2$. In such a case the two probabilities are $1 - \exp(-e(i)/T)$ and $\exp(-e(i)/T)$. If there is a gap between $e(1)$ and $e(2)$ then as $T \rightarrow 0$ the particle is in state $e(1)$ i.e. has an entropy of 0. If there is no gap then one has a problem as $e(2) - e(1) \rightarrow 0$, but $T \rightarrow 0$ as well. Thus it seems that a gap must be introduced in order that entropy behave properly as already argued in (1).

This gap for the particle in a box, however, violates Newtonian mechanics which allows all momentum p values. As a result given that a gap is needed it may also be the case that e_1 does not correspond to $p_1=0$ as in Newtonian mechanics.

We used the term box above and argue that the concept of equilibrium and T seem to apply to a confined system i.e one with a length constraint for a 1D example.. For example, the Boltzmann factor $\exp(-e/T)$ may be derived considering probability densities $n(e(i))$ with $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ and $n(e_1)n(e_2) = n(e_3)n(e_4)$. This is the reaction balance approach, but it seems that the particle must be confined for such an approach to even be defined. Thus we argue that there is something "special" occurring due to this constraint i.e. confinement in space. If energy has gaps then for a particle in a box: $\text{energy} = p^2/2m$ so $p = \text{momentum}$ itself must have gaps. Furthermore these gaps must be somehow linked to the length of the box. Thus momentum is being linked (and energy too) with length. In fact, given that one has gaps and uniformity throughout the 1D box, one may consider the length being broken into integer equal sized portions L/n . This is already a crude notion of a wavelength and leads to the idea of allowed p momentum values being associated with L/n in some manner.

Finally we note that Fermat's principle already links an invariant space variable with momentum conservation in the same direction. The classical analogue is Maupertuis' principle for particles with rest mass. In both cases one may link these approaches with the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$ which happens to be both the relativistic and nonrelativistic classical actions of a free particle. $dA/dx \text{ partial} = p$ so an eigenvalue equation is: $-id/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$ with b/p representing the wavelength. Thus one has a frequency proportional to $1/E$ and a wavelength proportional to $1/p$. Any p , however, is allowed so there is no gap. There is, however, an association of length with p . Thus if a box with a T has a length constraint one may suggest fitting integer numbers of sine wave crests into the box to create the "gap" required by entropy considerations.

Planck's Approach

As noted in (1) Planck's approach to the blackbody radiation problem uses ideas taken from Boltzmann's statistical approach in particular the probability factor $\exp(-e/T)$ where e is energy and T is temperature. In (1) two calculations are done. The first assumes no gap between e values so:

$$E_{ave} = N \int_0^\infty e \exp(-e/T) / \{ \int_0^\infty \exp(-e/T) \} = NT \quad (\text{we set } k \text{ from } kT \text{ to } 1) \quad ((1))$$

$$\text{And } S = \int_0^\infty dT (1/T) dE/dT = N \ln(T/T_0) \quad ((2))$$

((2)) already leads to trouble because one has to introduce a cutoff temperature T_0 such that $T > T_0$. Otherwise entropy \rightarrow infinite as $T \rightarrow 0$. Thus the idea of continuous energy does not work. (We note that in the blackbody radiation problem one considers oscillator modes as representing the allowed energies.)

In (1) it is suggested that one consider discrete energy levels in the following manner: $e = n b$ where b is a constant and $n=1,2,3,\dots$ etc. This allows for the use of the mathematics of a geometric series and calculate:

$$E_{ave} = \text{Sum over } n=1,2, \dots \quad b n \exp(-bn/T) / \text{Normalization} = - d/d(T/b) \text{ Sum over } n \exp(-bn/T) / \text{normalization}$$

The result is a function of b the gap in energy levels given in (1). This expression yields an entropy which tends to 0 as $T \rightarrow 0$ which is desired. Thus discrete energy levels are needed.

Particle in a Box and Two Levels

Instead of considering light and oscillators with $e=bn$ $n=1,2,3,\dots$ we consider a particle in a box with two levels i.e two momenta for simplicity. Then the probabilities are:

$$1 - \exp(-e_1/T) \quad \text{and} \quad \exp(-e_2/T) \quad \text{where } e_1 = p_1^2/2m \quad \text{and} \quad e_2 = p_2^2/2m \quad ((3))$$

For $T \rightarrow 0$ one wishes the particle to be in a single state i.e 0 entropy, thus if $e_2 = e_1 + b$ where b is a constant gap then the two probabilities become 1, 0 which is desired. Thus a constant gap emerges in this picture in a simpler manner than the Planck calculation. If the $e_1 - e_2 \rightarrow 0$ as $T \rightarrow 0$ there is trouble.

A question still remains: What causes the gap? We argue that to have a statistical problem (equilibrium) and a T temperature in the first place one assumes a constraint namely the length of a box. It is true that one may make the box large or small, but nevertheless one has the constraint. For example in the reaction balance approach to finding Boltzmann's factor $\exp(-e/T)$

one may consider elastic collisions $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ ((4a)) with densities $n(e_1)n(e_2) = n(e_3)n(e_4)$ ((4b)). If there is no confinement it seems one cannot really consider such a balanced reaction. (One then takes \ln of ((4b)) and links to ((4a))).

Thus we argue that the energy gap is somehow linked to the length of the box L for a 1D box. Thus both e and $pp/2m$ must be associated with this suggestion. Given that the box is uniform we suggest breaking it into equally spaced compartments each characterized by an integer i.e. L/n . This we argue is a crude notion of wavelength and leads to gaps in energy if momentum is somehow a function of (L/n) . The question is then: How does one link momentum/energy to L/n ?

Fermat's and Maupertuis' Principles

We have argued in previous notes (2) that Fermat's least time principle for light actually varies time with respect to an invariant spatial variable (x if the mirror or medium surface is in the x direction). This in turn leads to conservation of momentum in the direction of the invariant spatial variable. Thus (p_x) is directly linked to x , in fact $(p_x)x$ gives an expression such that d/dx from Fermat's principle yields (p_x) the conserved quantity. Almost identical ideas hold for particles with rest mass and Maupertuis' Principle which varies $\int dt \sum_i p(i) dq(i)/dt$ (2). Here $i=1,2$ may apply to two regions one with a constant potential of V_1 and the other with a constant potential of V_2 . $dq(i)/dt = v(i) = \text{velocity in region } i$. The variation is of t which is the same as time variation in Fermat's principle.

This relationship is strengthened by the form $A = -Et + px$ which is the relativistic and nonrelativistic classical action as well as a Lorentz invariant. The point we wish to make is that one has a link between p and x , namely there is a wavelength that is proportional to $1/p$. Thus one may associate p with n/L i.e. the equally spaced units discussed in the above section. Energy then is associated with $pp/2m$ and also has gaps (although they are not equally spaced as in Planck's scenario). In particular one has the eigenvalue equation $-id/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$ and so one may fit sine crests/troughs in each of the units.

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that applying Boltzmann's factor $\exp(-e/T)$ to a particle in a box with two levels (for simplicity) leads to the two probabilities $P(e_1) = \exp(-e_1/T)$ and $P(e_2) = 1 - \exp(-e_1/T)$. For $T \rightarrow 0$ one wishes to have 0 entropy i.e. the particle in one state i.e. e_1 so $e_2 - e_1 = \text{constant}$ allows for this. If $e_2 - e_1 \rightarrow 0$ and $T \rightarrow 0$ one has trouble.

Thus one expects a gap, but this violates Newtonian mechanics which allows for any momentum and hence e state. Thus taking the energy gap seriously suggests that e_1 may not even be $p_1 = 0$ as in Newtonian mechanics. We suggest that it seems the only reason for a gap is a constraint in the length of the 1D box (example). We suggest a box is needed in order to have a statistical problem and the notion of T in the first place. (One may always expand the size of the box, but a length is present.) Given that the box is uniform we suggest equally spaced units of L/n . This is the notion of a wavelength, but is still crude.

We next consider how to link the wavelength to momentum. Using ideas from Fermat's principle which associates (p_x) with x i.e. $(p_x)x$ or the Lorentz invariant $-Et + px$ which is both the

free particle relativistic and nonrelativistic action with $v=x/t$, we suggest that wavelength is proportional to $1/p$ or p is proportional to n/L in the partitioned box picture. Then $e= pp/2m$ and so there is a gap in energy (although it is not equally spaced). From $A=-Et+px$, $dA/dx \text{ partial} = p$ so an eigenvalue equation is $-id/dx \text{ partial} \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA)$. Thus $\exp(ipx)$ leads to a picture such that an integer number of sine wave crests/troughs may fit in the box. This is more quantitative than simply partitioning the box

References

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